

Promising High Yielding Brinjal Variety Gujarat Round Brinjal -10 (NavNidhi)

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INTRODUCTION:

Brinjal commonly known as eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.) is a versatile crop adapted to different agro-climatic regions of India and can be grown throughout the year (Nayak and Sharma, 2013). Looking to its year-around availability, brinjal is referred to as the common man's vegetable in the Indian subcontinent (Saini *et al.*, 2019). Being an often cross pollinated crop, natural intercrossing brought extensive genetic diversity of eggplant cultivars grown all over the world (Rathod *et al.*, 2023). The varieties of

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ABSTRACT

Vegetable crop improvement programme in India have concentrated on development of improved varieties with high yield and nutritive values along with abiotic and biotic stress resistance for cultivation at various locations across the country. GRB-10 has been developed through recombination breeding using cross between NBL-13 X NBL-147 utilizing the pedigree method of plant breeding at the Vegetable Research Farm, regional Horticulture Research Station, NAU, Navsari. GRB-10 was evaluated in various trials across Gujarat during 2018-19 to 2022-23 and showcased 396.33 q/ha production with 11.81 %, 10.96 %, 16.15 % and 19.56% increased fruit yield over standard checks *viz.*, GNRB-1 (354.46 q/ha fruit yield), GAOB-2 (357.20 q/ha), GRB-5 (345.11 q/ha) and Swarna Mani (331.49 q/ha), respectively. It endows with special attributes *viz.*, round shaped light purple fruits with medium pistil scar and green calyx at harvest. Its high yield potential and consumer preference will play a significant role in improving the productivity and sustainability of brinjal cultivation in south Gujarat.

brinjal display a wide range of varietal differences mainly the shape, colour and size of fruits but the attributes *viz.*, chemical composition, earliness, environmental requirements *etc.*, are also taken into consideration.

India is the second largest producer of brinjal in the world accounting for about one third of world's brinjal production. In India, brinjal is cultivated in almost all the states. West Bengal, Odisha, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh and Bihar are the major brinjal producing states. In the year 2024-25, brinjal was cultivated across 689 thousand hectares, resulting in an annual

production of 131.31 lakh tonnes in India (Anonymous, 2025).

Gujarat state owing to diverse climatic conditions, from sub-tropical to tropical and arid to semi-arid, brinjal is cultivated almost in all the districts across the state. Changing climatic condition has adversely affected production and productivity of vegetables. In order to fulfill the demand of vegetables in the region the production needs to be raised by increasing productivity.

Keeping in view of the above facts, efforts have been made for development of high yielding pest-disease resistant and climate-resilient brinjal varieties using pedigree selection which can play a significant role in uplifting the production of brinjal crop.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The brinjal variety GRB-10 has been developed through recombination breeding using cross between NBL-13 X NBL-147 utilizing the pedigree method of plant breeding at the Vegetable Research Farm, Regional Horticulture Research Station, NAU, Navsari. This variety was tested as genotype NBR 18-01 in PET during 2018-19 and onwards in different trials over locations in the Gujarat state *viz.*, Navsari, Junagadh, Anand, Ladol and Waghai from the year 2020-21 to 2022-23. It was also evaluated at different locations of south Gujarat region also. This genotype was also contributed in AICRP (VC) since 2022 for national testing.

In the field experiment, each genotype was planted in randomized block design consisting three replications with the spacing of 90 x 60 cm following recommended agronomical practices. The observation on growth, yield as well as its contributing characters was noted from five randomly selected plants in each plot at different stages of crop growth. The data along with the pest and disease reactions and agronomic performance was utilized to identify the best performing genotype. The variety was characterized with 34 morphological characters based on DUS testing norms. Molecular profiling

of GRB-10 was performed along with standard checks *viz.*, GAOB-2, Swarna Mani, GNRB-1, GRB-5 using ISSR primer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Fruit yield and yield attributes:

The brinjal variety GRB-10 (Nav Nidhi) was evaluated in various multi-location trials across Gujarat state during 2018-19 to 2022-23, on an average it recorded 396.33 q/ha production with 11.81 %, 10.96 %, 16.15 % and 19.56% increased fruit yield over standard checks *viz.*, GNRB-1 (354.46 q/ha), GAOB-2 (357.20 q/ha), GRB-5 (345.11 q/ha) and Swarna Mani (331.49 q/ha), respectively (Table 1) Under South Gujarat condition, NBR-18-01 registered 8.91%, 10.64%, 11.93% and 13.33% fruit yield superiority over GNRB-1, GAOB-2, GRB-5 and Swarna Mani, respectively, while, in Middle Gujarat zone NBR-18-01 obtained 15.96%, 12.52%, 19.72% and 21.70% fruit yield superiority over GNRB-1, GAOB-2, GRB-5 and Swarna Mani, respectively. In Saurashtra region, NBR-18-01 recorded 20.99%, 18.01%, 19.99% and 25.64% fruit yield superiority over GNRB-1, GAOB-2, GRB-5 and Swarna Mani, respectively. However, in North Gujarat Zone, NBR-18-01 did not achieved superiority over the checks GNRB-1 and GAOB-2, while, it achieved 20.35% and 42.07% superiority over the checks GRB-5 and Swarna Mani, respectively.

Looking to the performance of the brinjal variety GRB-10 (Nav Nidhi), it has been proposed for recommendation for general cultivation in late *Kharif/rabi* season in brinjal growing areas of the Gujarat state.

Quality parameters:

The characters *viz.*, total phenol, TSS, anthocyanin and glycoalkaloids, being important quality parameters of brinjal, were measured at 5th harvest of brinjal fruits for comparison among the tested entries. GRB-10 (Nav Nidhi) contains 68.44 GAE/100g of total Phenol, 2.77 % of total sugar, 19.32 mg/100g of anthocyanin and 8.61 mg/100g

of glycoalkaloids (Table-2). It recorded 19.32 mg/100g anthocyanin content which is higher than the checks GAOB-2 (19.20 mg/100g) and GRB-5 (2.92 mg/100g). The purple colour of GRB-10 fruit is due to the presence of anthocyanins pigment in the peel which is in accordance with (Sadilova *et al.*, 2006) and (Rathod *et al.*, 2023). The traders and consumers have appreciated fruits of this genotype owing to its attractive light purple fruit skin colour with medium glossy and soft flesh. However, in case of glycoalkaloids, GRB-10 contains 8.61 mg/100g which is lower than the check GNRB-1 (8.82 mg/100g) and GAOB-2 (9.36 mg/100g). In addition to this, GRB-10 contains 2.77 % of total sugar which is higher than the checks GNRB-1 (2.31%) and Swarna Mani (2.62%). Total soluble

sugars in brinjal, enhances palatability of the fruit by increasing the sweetness (Tirkey *et al.*, 2018). Thus, total sugars play an important role in consumer preference by imparting taste, quality and nutritional value. The phenol content is associated with antioxidant capacity as well as resistance against disease and pest in various crops (Mori *et al.*, 2017). Various studies have also reported a good correlation between the total phenol content of plant extracts and antioxidant activity (Kandolia *et al.*, 2015).

Reaction to pests and diseases:

Most important feature of GRB-10 (Nav Nidhi) variety is, it has less prevalence of little leaf disease and less infestation of shoot and fruit borer damage as compared to checks.

Table 1: Performance of GRB-10 (Nav Nidhi) for fruit yield and yield contributing Characters

Variety	Fruit Yield (q/ha)	No. of fruit/plant	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit girth (cm)	Fruit weight (g)	Days to first picking	Plant height (cm)	No. of primary branches
GRB-10	396.33	23.99	9.39	17.93	79.17	66.67	83.72	5.64
Standards								
GNRB-1	354.46	20.47	9.12	16.88	78.50	67.00	93.18	5.19
GAOB-2	357.20	20.22	9.15	17.69	73.40	70.33	79.20	5.71
GRB-5	345.11	17.33	10.12	19.06	75.82	70.67	94.07	4.82
S. Mani	331.49	16.08	10.41	19.94	87.27	70.00	90.12	5.07

Table 2: Performance of GRB-10 (Nav Nidhi) for quality attributes in state varietal trials

Variety	Total Phenol (GAE/100g)	Vitamin C (mg/100g of edible portion)	Total Sugars (%)	Crude fibre (%)	Glycoalkaloids (mg/100g)	Anthocyanin (mg/100g)
GRB-10	68.44	2.63	2.77	1.62	8.61	19.32
Standards						
GNRB-1	64.23	2.20	2.31	1.44	8.82	20.44
GAOB-2	69.00	2.60	2.90	1.38	9.36	19.20
GRB-5	48.00	2.30	3.17	1.36	7.38	2.92
S. Mani	83.16	2.32	2.62	1.57	6.04	21.21

Table 3: Morphological characteristics of brinjal variety GRB-10 (Nav Nidhi)

Sr. No.	Characters	GRB-10
1.	Seedling: Anthocyanin colouration of hypocotyls	Absent
2.	Stem: Anthocyanin colouration	Absent
3.	Stem : Pubescence	Medium
4.	Leaf : Length	Medium
5.	Leaf : Width	Medium
6.	Leaf : Margin	Sinuate
7.	Leaf : Blistering	Absent
8.	Leaf :Spininess	Absent
9.	Leaf : Blade colour	Green
10.	Leaf : Intensity of colour of blade	Medium
11.	Leaf : Colour of vein	Green
12.	Leaf : Intensity of colour of vein	Medium
13.	Inflorescence : Number of flowers	1 to 3
14.	Flower : Size	Medium
15.	Flower : Colour	Light purple
16.	Fruit: General Shape	Round
17.	Fruit: Diameter of pistil Scar	Medium
18.	Fruit: Shape of apex	Round
19.	Fruit: Colour of skin at commercial harvesting	Light purple
20.	Fruit: Intensity of purple colour of skin	Medium
21.	Fruit: Stripes	Absent
22.	Fruit: Patches	Absent
23.	Fruit: Glossiness at marketable stage	Medium
24.	Fruit: Size of calyx	Medium
25.	Fruit: Colour of calyx	Green
26.	Fruit: Intensity of colour of calyx	Medium
27.	Fruit: Spininess of Calyx	Absent
28.	Fruit: Rib	Absent
29.	Fruit: Colour of flesh	Whitish
30.	Fruit: Length of pedicel	Medium
31.	Fruiting: Pattern	Mixed
32.	Plant: Growth habit	Semi spreading
33.	Plant: Spread (distance between two extremes leaf tips at widest point)	Medium
34.	Fruit: Colour of skin at marketable stage	Light Purple

(Plant growth habit, fruit colour, shape and flower colour)
Fig. 1. Morphological features of GRB-10 (Nav Nidhi)

Morphological characters of the variety GRB-10 (Nav Nidhi):

- Fruits are round, light purple in colour and medium glossy.
- Plants are semi spreading, medium tall with 5-6 branches.
- Flowers are medium in size with purple petals.
- Calyx is medium in size and green in colour (Table-3).

A national indent number, IC 651321 was allotted to the variety GRB-10 by NBPGR, New Delhi. The variety was notified for release by the Central Committee on Crop Standards, Notification and Release of Varieties for Agricultural Crops, vide the Gazette of India notification S.O. 4000 (E) dated 1st September, 2025.

Fig 2: ISSR Profiling of Brinjal produced by UBC 807, UBC 808, UBC 809, UBC 810, UBC 811, UBC 812, UBC 815

Note: L-100bp ladder, 1:NBR-18-01, 2:GAOB-2(C), 3:Swarna Mani, 4:GNRB-1(C), 5:GRB-5(C)

Distinguishing characteristics and molecular profiling of the brinjal variety GRB 10 (Nav Nidhi):

ISSR primer UBC 807 generated a prominent bands of 863 and 666bp in NBR-18-01, GAOB-2(C), Swarna Mani, that was absent in GNRB-1(C), GRB-5(C). Unique band of 792bp was amplified by UBC 808 in GAOB-2(C). ISSR primer UBC 809 generated prominent bands of 851bp in NBR-18-01, GAOB-2(C), Swarna Mani, that was absent in GNRB-1(C), GRB-5(C). ISSR primer UBC 811 generated a prominent bands of 384bp in, GAOB-2(C), Swarna Mani, GNRB-1(C), GRB-5(C) that was absent in NBR-18-01. Unique band of 1123bp was amplified by UBC 812 in NBR-18-01. ISSR primer UBC 810 generated a prominent bands of 746 and 617bp in NBR-18-01, GAOB-2(C), Swarna Mani, that was

absent in GNRB-1(C), GRB-5(C). ISSR primer UBC 815 showed monomorphic bands.

RECOMMENDATION:

GRB-10 (Nav Nidhi) is a high yielding brinjal variety suitable for cultivation in *Kharif* and *Rabi* season, at 90 cm row spacing under normal environmental, irrigated condition in Gujarat. It required 400-500 g seeds for planting one hectare area. Its high yield and better quality will play a significant role in improving the productivity, profitability and sustainability of brinjal cultivation in Gujarat.

FUTURE SCOPE

In future, this variety can be exploited commercially to increase quality production of brinjal and can also be used as a parent in hybridization.

Conflict of Interest. None

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